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salts were all B.D.H., AnalaR grade samples. Ethanol solvent was purified as described earlier⁶.

The experimental method consisted of the well known Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁷. In the titrations of the potassium salts of Schiff bases derived from the dibasic aspartic and glutamic acids, 0.2 M HClO₄ was used instead of 0.1 M HClO₄.

Stabilities of Some Bivalent Metal Complexes of Salicylaldehyde and Substituted Salicylaldehyde-Aminoacid Schiff Bases

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SOME bivalent metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde and glycine have been investigated by Eichhorn and Marchand¹ spectrophotometrically and by Leussing *et al.*² potentiometrically in aqueous solution. Apart from these, there is not much report on the complexes of other amino acids. We report here the results of our studies involving the amino acids, glycine, α -alanine, aspartic acid and glutamic acid, and aromatic aldehydes, such as salicylaldehyde, 5-methyl-, 5-chloro- and 5-bromo-salicylaldehydes. The systems involving salicylaldehyde have been studied both in aqueous as well as in 50% (v/v) ethanolic media, while, the substituted salicylaldehyde systems have been studied only in the latter.

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde (E. Merck) used was freshly distilled under reduced pressure. The 5-methyl-, 5-chloro- and 5-bromo-salicylaldehydes were prepared by reported methods³⁻⁵.

Among the α -amino acids, glycine and glutamic acids were E. Merck products and α -alanine and aspartic acids were of B.D.H. make. The metal

Results and Discussion

The stabilities of the metal complexes of any given ligand depend on the magnitude of the acid dissociation constant of the ligand. They have been calculated in this work as practical protonation constants, according to the method of Irving and Rossotti⁶. Table 1 summarises the acid dissociation constants determined in this work, some in aqueous and some in 50% ethanolic medium. The pK_1^H values listed are associated with the dissociation of the carboxylic proton and the pK_2^H with that of the hydroxylic proton.

The calculation of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL have been made by considering the ligands as biprotic. The $\log K_1$ and $\log \beta_2$ values have been obtained both by the half-integral method as well as the least square method, where the range of \bar{n} lay between 0 and 2.0. In other cases, they were obtained by the half-integral method only.

Table 2 summarises the stability constants of the metal complexes of some of the Schiff bases studied in aqueous medium, while Table 3 summarises the results obtained in 50% ethanolic medium at 30°.

Cu(II) seems to show little tendency to form 1 : 2 complexes in aqueous medium, in contrast with Ni(II), Zn(II) and Co(II). This, however, is not true of the 50% ethanolic medium. This may probably be due to specific solvent effects. Zn(II) alone seems to have a tendency to form 1 : 3 complexes both in aqueous and 50% ethanolic media. It has been pointed out on the basis of its magnetic moment⁸ that Zn(II) is the only one that cannot form octahedral complexes. On both these grounds, it

TABLE 1—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF SCHIFF BASES FORMED BY SALICYLALDEHYDE AND AMINOACIDS AT 20°, 30° AND 40°

	pK_1^H			pK_2^H		
	20°	30°	40°	20°	30°	40°
In aqueous medium						
i) Salicylidene-glycine	10.01	9.80	9.74	8.96	8.25	8.12
ii) Salicylidene- α -alanine	10.37	9.89	9.53	8.23	7.91	7.97
iii) Salicylidene-aspartic acid	—	9.77	—	—	7.92	—
iv) Salicylidene-glutamic acid	—	9.49	—	—	7.79	—
In 50% aqueous ethanol medium						
i) Salicylidene-glycine	—	9.92	—	—	8.35	—
ii) 5-Methylsalicylidene-glycine	—	9.80	—	—	8.40	—
iii) 5-Chloro-salicylidene-glycine	—	9.78	—	—	7.65	—
iv) 5-Bromo-salicylidene-glycine	—	9.57	—	—	7.63	—

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES OF SOME SCHIFF BASES IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM AT 30°

Ligand	Cu(II)		Ni(II)		Zn(II)			Co(II)	
	log K ₁	log β ₂	log K ₁	log β ₂	log K ₁	log β ₂	log β ₃	log K ₁	log β ₂
Salicylidene-glycine	12.55	—	7.67	11.41	7.05	—	—	—	—
Salicylidene-α-alanine	11.44	—	6.49	9.97	6.50	11.58	15.60	—	—
Salicylidene-aspartic acid	14.00	—	8.42	—	7.32	10.46	—	8.50	11.53
Salicylidene-glutamic acid	10.46	—	8.78	11.35	7.28	11.30	—	7.40	10.82

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES OF SOME SCHIFF BASES IN 50% ETHANOLIC MEDIUM AT 30°

Ligand	Cu(II)		Ni(II)		Zn(II)			Co(II)			Mn(II)	
	log K ₁	log β ₂	log K ₁	log β ₂	log K ₁	log β ₂	log β ₃	log K ₁	log β ₂	log β ₃	log K ₁	log β ₂
Salicylidene-glycine	14.38	18.27	10.58	15.59	9.76	14.91	18.36	9.38	13.57	—	6.68	10.01
5-Chloro-salicylidene-glycine	13.10	16.91	8.83	12.83	8.99	13.64	16.54	9.12	13.05	—	6.65	11.01
5-Bromo-salicylidene-glycine	13.60	—	10.71	16.96	9.68	15.24	18.59	9.71	15.50	18.2	5.87	9.27
5-Methyl-salicylidene-glycine	14.61	18.20	10.67	15.47	9.98	14.50	—	9.67	13.90	—	6.63	10.44

appears that the Zn(II) complexes have a different type of coordination and structure than the other complexes, which are known to form the octahedral complexes.

An examination of the log K₁ values of the metal complexes in Table 2 shows that the order of stabilities is Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Zn(II) in most cases, and in the two cases studied the order is Co(II) > Ni(II) > Zn(II). This order is not much different from the Irving-Williams order of Mn(II) < Fe(II) < Co(II) < Ni(II) < Cu(II) > Zn(II).

The stabilities of the Schiff base complexes depend primarily on the strength of the C=N bond, the basicity of the imino group, the denticity of the Schiff base and steric factors¹⁰. The presence of the CH₃ substituent in α-alanine definitely lowers the stability constant by making the imine nitrogen less basic and hence a weaker donor of electrons to the metal ions. However, it is difficult to explain why the aspartic acid-Schiff base complexes are stronger than the glutamic acid-Schiff base complexes, which are both stronger than the glycine- or the α-alanine-Schiff base complexes, on the basis of the strength of the C=N bond and the basicities of the imine nitrogen only. A possible explanation in terms of the steric aspect of their structures has been given elsewhere¹¹.

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Electro Reduction of *Cis-Trans*-Isomers of Co(III) Complexes of the Type

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EXTENSIVE studies have been made previously on the geometric isomers of various metal ions¹⁻³, using different techniques. Recently, the polarographic technique has been successfully used for the purpose of identification of *cis-trans*-isomers of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{SO}_3)_2]^-$.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H., AnalaR grade. The solutions were prepared in double distilled water. An automatic pen recording CIC (Baroda, India) polarograph was used to record the polarograms. Purified nitrogen gas was used for removing the dissolved oxygen.